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Results of the modeling of air flow movement through the gas filters of different types

The use of gas filters in the workplace is an important element of the system of measures to protect the health of workers in potentially hazardous conditions [1]. Gas filters help remove harmful and toxic substances from the air inhaled by workers, such as gases, vapors, smoke and other substances. The use of gas filters can prevent poisoning, respiratory tract damage, allergic reactions and other negative consequences of exposure to harmful and hazardous substances on the human body. Thus, the use of gas filters contributes to increasing the overall level of safety and health of workers in the workplace.

The type and class of the filter is determined by testing the products under standard methods and stable conditions, namely constant air flow through the filter and the concentration of the harmful substance in the air of the test chamber. Such conditions are not found in workplaces. Thus, the intensity and depth of the worker's inhalation varies depending on the type of work performed, which leads to a constant change in the flow rate of the harmful substance passing through the gas filter. Similarly, the concentration of harmful substances in the inhaled air can vary depending on the distance to the source of pollution.

In scientific research and modeling of the process of filtering harmful substances through layers of coal for gas filters, air flow models through special columns filled with the above-mentioned coal are mainly used. Such models can theoretically take into account the influence of the point of entry of contaminated air and its exit from the test column. However, they do not take into account real filtration through gas filters, where the points of entry and exit of air are determined not only by scientific calculations, but also by practical issues regarding the manufacturability of manufacturing such a filter and the ergonomics of its use.

The quality and physical characteristics of activated carbon (grain size, their porosity, geometric shape of grains, absence of moisture in grains, etc.) have a direct impact on the gas filter breakthrough time.

Therefore, there is a need to determine the real breakthrough time of filters taking into account the parameters of activated carbon and the geometric shape of the gas filter housing.

To determine the protective action time t_b , the following formula is most often used:

$$t_b = \frac{W_e W}{C_0 Q} - \frac{W_e \rho_B}{k_V C_0} \ln \left(\frac{C_0 - C}{C} \right)$$

where W_e – sorption capacity of activated carbon, g/g, W – mass of activated carbon, g, C_0 – concentration of harmful substance, g/cm³, Q – air flow rate passing through activated carbon, cm³/min, ρ_B – packing density of activated carbon granules, g/cm³, k_V – adsorption rate coefficient, min⁻¹, C – penetration concentration determined for a certain substance, g/cm³.

The first part of the equation considers ideal conditions when all activated carbon has completely reacted with the harmful substance in the adsorption reaction. The second part of the equation takes into account factors that reduce the time of the filter's protective action, so it has a minus sign.

The disadvantage of this approach is that this equation does not take into account, in particular, the influence of the parameters of the container in which this activated carbon will be used.

The filter box into which the activated carbon is poured is not ideal, so part of the carbon does not take part in the process of purifying polluted air from harmful substances, or does not take part in full.

Figure 1. Dynamic tube for activated carbon testing (a) and its placement in the temperature normalization unit (b)

Typically, a dynamic tube (Fig. 1) containing the tested activated carbon is used to determine the time of protective action in laboratory conditions.

This technique allows the maximum involvement of activated carbon grains in the dynamic tube for testing, and therefore to determine its characteristics more accurately. However, in such a tube, the coal is not as compacted as it would be in a

gas filter canister, so the pore size will not correspond to the conditions of real application.

The adsorption front in this case is difficult to estimate, since the diameter of the dynamic tube is 20 mm, and the diameter of a real filter, for example, filter of 1 class cylindrical form is not less than 75 mm.

Therefore, there is a need to determine how air layers will be distributed in the middle of gas filters canister depending on their shape.

Figures 2-7 show the results of modeling in the SolidWorks software environment.

Figure 2. Gas filter flat form at air flow rates of 15 l/min.

Figure 3. Gas filter flat form at air flow rates of 47.5 l/min

Figure 4. Gas filter cylindrical form at air flow rates of 15 l/min

Figure 5. Gas filter cylindrical form at air flow rates of 47.5 l/min

Figure 6. Airflow through a dynamic tube with a resistance of 100 Pa

Figure 7. Airflow through a dynamic tube with a resistance of 700 Pa

References

1. https://www.osha.gov/publications/respiratory_protection_bulletin_2011